

1 **Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes: PHF21a.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We recently described (1) a mechanism of transcriptional regulation, in human cancer and in
7 development, wherein the non-coding RNA responsible for X-inactivation, Xist, is modulated in the
8 presence of p53 mutation, or induced following loss of p53 tumor suppression, representing a novel and
9 biologically relevant method of transcriptional regulation in solid tumors.

10 To understand the precise mechanism by which Xist exerts ectopic function in human cancer, we studied
11 whole transcription in human cells genetically engineered to contain an Xist transgene (10) to identify Xist
12 interactants.

13 We provide evidence here indicating the presence of PHF21a (BHC20) in a cell- or tumor -type specific
14 RNP complex containing Xist.

Methods

We studied differential gene expression in p53 wild-type and p53 deficient breast cancer cells, where Xist modulation by p53 was discovered, in human cells transgenically expressing Xist, and in embryonic stem cells from mice genetically engineered to lack p53 expression using the R-based application GEO2R. GSE57083 was generated using Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array microarray technology with $n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with wild-type p53 (MCF7 and ZR751) and $n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with mutant p53 (T47D and BT549); platform GPL570 was utilized. GSE26362 was generated using Affymetrix Mouse Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] microarray technology with $n=2$ wild-type embryonic stem cells (R1E) and $n=2$ p53 $-/-$ embryonic stem cells (129X1 x 129S1); platform GPL6246 was utilized. GSE68109 was generated using Illumina HiSeq 2500 (Homo sapiens) RNA-sequencing technology with $n=1$ HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (day 1; no doxycycline) and $n=2$ HT-1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with Xist integration (day 5; doxycycline induction); platform GPL16791 was utilized. We used SEEK for computational co-regulation study (12).

Results

We previously utilized published mass spectrometric data to deconvolute the composition of this hypothetical complex, revealing the RNA-binding protein KHDRBS1 was a *bona fide* protein interaction partner of Xist (2). We continued here discovery and description of an Xist RNP complex using p53 wild-type and deficient cancer cells, cells genetically engineered to express Xist, p53 deficient mouse embryonic stem cells where Xist is induced, and using a systems biological methodology which probes whole transcription across multiple settings to discover transcriptionally co-regulated genes.

Chart 1: PHF21a is transcriptionally activated in p53 deficient cancer cells concomitant with Xist modulation.

GSE57083

$n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with wild-type p53 (MCF7 and ZR751)

$n=2$ breast cancer cell lines with mutant p53 (T47D and BT549)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
224589_at	0.0000218	2.87E+01	-4.25	5.14489344	XIST	2/54675	
1558965_at	0.1304554	-1.95	-4.47	-0.62429179	PHF21A	7070/54675	

In p53 deficient cell lines where we had discovered control of Xist by p53, we found transcriptional induction of PHF21A.

To continue to study a relationship between Xist and PHF21, we examined whole transcription in human cells genetically engineered to express Xist (Chart 2).

Chart 2: Expression of Xist in humans is associated with transcriptional induction of PHF21a

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (day 1; no doxycycline [DOX])

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 8p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	% DE
7503	0	0.0949	-5.07E+01	-4.81	42145.57	XIST	1/18377	99.99
51317	3.00E-10	0.1479	-6.3	-9.31E-01	1073.28	PHF21A	387/18377	97.9

Expression of Xist resulted in transcriptional induction of PHF21a in human cells transgenically engineered to express Xist (Chart 2). The data demonstrated that expression of Xist in human cells was sufficient to result in differential expression of PHF21a.

We next evaluated whole transcription in mouse embryonic stem cells with engineered deletion of p53, in which we have previously demonstrated Xist induction (1).

Chart 3: Deletion of p53 in mouse embryonic stem cells, which results in modest Xist induction (1), is accompanied by differential expression of the RNA-binding protein KHDRBS1.

GSE26362

n=2 wild-type embryonic stem cells (R1E)

n=2 p53 *-/-* embryonic stem cells (129X1 x 129S1)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
10606178	2.44e-07	-13.3827038	7.26104	-1.24452642	Xist	2894/ 28815	90.0 (1)
10474006	1.04E-05	8.6390903	3.194392	1.48606725	Phf21a	6268/28815	78.2

PHF21a was modestly differentially expressed upon deletion of p53 (Chart 3), which co-occurred with Xist induction (1). In mouse ES cells, PHF21a was repressed upon p53 deletion and Xist induction; this may reflect species- or p53 mutation status-specific differences in Xist RNP complex composition.

After establishing that expression of PHF21a was controlled by Xist in human cells expressing Xist, we examined transcriptional co-regulation by PHF21a to understand if PHF21a was co-regulated with genes to which have previously described as belonging to the Xist RNP, including KHDRBS1, ILF2 and ILF3.

We interrogated a computational co-regulation tool known as SEEK (12), which queries whole transcriptome expression patterns across a variety of cellular contexts, identifying in an unbiased fashion the Xist RNP components KHDRBS1 and ILF3 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: KHDRBS1 and ILF3 are PHF21a co-regulated gene products.

Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	PHF21A	51317	-3.2	0.0025		

Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	KHDRBS1	10657	1.69	0.0112	61/17862	99.7
	ILF3	3609	1.815	0.0238	27/17862	99.8

Xist interacts with known localization factors, including SPEN, CIZ, and ATRX. We studied transcriptional co-regulation by PHF21a to understand whether PHF21a was co-regulated with any known Xist interacting proteins (Chart 4). We found PHF21a was closely co-regulated with SPEN, CIZ and ATRX. Thus, PHF21a existed in a transcriptional co-regulated network with known Xist-interacting proteins as well as genes we described as belonging to a novel Xist RNP complex (Chart 4 and Figure 1).

1 Chart 4: SPEN, CIZ, and ATRX, Xist-interacting proteins, are PHF21a co-regulated genes.

2
3 Query genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	PHF21A	51317	-3.2	0.0025		

4
5 Coexpressed genes:

Rank	Gene	Entrez ID	Coexpression Score	p-value	Rank	%Co-reg
	SPEN	23013	1.335	0.0312	329/17862	98.2
	ATRX	546	1.615	0.0208	93/17862	99.5
	CIZ1	25792	1.4258	0.0272	209/17862	98.8

6
7
8
9 **Discussion**

10
11 p53 controls Xist expression in certain cellular contexts, particularly in transformed states; Xist
12 controls expression of Xist binding partner PHF21a in human embryonic stem cells, and this is
13 independent of p53 status. The composition of the Xist RNP complex will likely vary by cell type, species,
14 and p53 status which often but not always governs transformation. This complex we predict functions to
15 drive tumor progression by enhancing fitness of tumor clones through genomic instability driven primarily
16 epigenetically. We provided here evidence indicating the presence of PHF21a (BHC20) in an
17 Xist-containing RNP complex.
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Mamoor, S., 2023. The tumor suppressor p53 regulates Xist expression in certain cellular contexts.
2. Mamoor, S., 2024. Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes.
3. Li, M., He, Y., Dubois, W., Wu, X., Shi, J. and Huang, J., 2012. Distinct regulatory mechanisms and functions for p53-activated and p53-repressed DNA damage response genes in embryonic stem cells. *Molecular cell*, 46(1), pp.30-42.
4. GSE57083. Astra Zeneca Cell Line Database. Oncology, Bioinformatics. Macclesfield, UK.
5. Chu, C., Zhang, Q.C., Da Rocha, S.T., Flynn, R.A., Bharadwaj, M., Calabrese, J.M., Magnuson, T., Heard, E. and Chang, H.Y., 2015. Systematic discovery of Xist RNA binding proteins. *Cell*, 161(2), pp.404-416.
6. Sunwoo, H., Colognori, D., Froberg, J.E., Jeon, Y. and Lee, J.T., 2017. Repeat E anchors Xist RNA to the inactive X chromosomal compartment through CDKN1A-interacting protein (CIZ1). *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(40), pp.10654-10659.
7. Minajigi, A., Froberg, J.E., Wei, C., Sunwoo, H., Kesner, B., Colognori, D., Lessing, D., Payer, B., Boukhali, M., Haas, W. and Lee, J.T., 2015. A comprehensive Xist interactome reveals cohesin repulsion and an RNA-directed chromosome conformation. *Science*, 349(6245), p.aab2276.
8. Pandya-Jones, A., Markaki, Y., Serizay, J., Chitashvili, T., Mancina Leon, W.R., Damianov, A., Chronis, C., Papp, B., Chen, C.K., McKee, R. and Wang, X.J., 2020. A protein assembly mediates Xist localization and gene silencing. *Nature*, 587(7832), pp.145-151.
9. Aguilar, R., Spencer, K.B., Kesner, B., Rizvi, N.F., Badmalia, M.D., Mrozowich, T., Mortison, J.D., Rivera, C., Smith, G.F., Burchard, J. and Dandliker, P.J., 2022. Targeting Xist with compounds that disrupt RNA structure and X inactivation. *Nature*, 604(7904), pp.160-166.
10. Sarma, K., Cifuentes-Rojas, C., Ergun, A., Del Rosario, A., Jeon, Y., White, F., Sadreyev, R. and Lee, J.T., 2014. ATRX directs binding of PRC2 to Xist RNA and Polycomb targets. *Cell*, 159(4), pp.869-883.
11. Li, M., He, Y., Dubois, W., Wu, X., Shi, J. and Huang, J., 2012. Distinct regulatory mechanisms and functions for p53-activated and p53-repressed DNA damage response genes in embryonic stem cells. *Molecular cell*, 46(1), pp.30-42.
12. Kelsey, A.D., Yang, C., Leung, D., Minks, J., Dixon-McDougall, T., Baldry, S.E., Bogutz, A.B., Lefebvre, L. and Brown, C.J., 2015. Impact of flanking chromosomal sequences on localization and silencing by the human non-coding RNA XIST. *Genome biology*, 16, pp.1-16.
13. Zhu, Q., Wong, A.K., Krishnan, A., Aure, M.R., Tadych, A., Zhang, R., Corney, D.C., Greene, C.S., Bongo, L.A., Kristensen, V.N. and Charikar, M., 2015. Targeted exploration and analysis of large cross-platform human transcriptomic compendia. *Nature methods*, 12(3), pp.211-214.